

There was no cultivar difference except at tillering.

Effect on yield components of different treatments are presented in Table 2. Percent productive tillers and grain weight per plant were highest in control plots and lowest with inoculation at booting in both IR42 and IR72.

Filled grain number per panicle did not significantly differ among treatments in both IR42 and IR72, but there were significant differences in 1000-grain weight, filled grain percentage, and total biomass per plant.

Control had the highest biomass/plant, followed by tillering and panicle initiation, in both the cultivars. Inoculated plants had the lowest biomass values at booting and flowering, but IR42 and IR72 did not differ significantly. Inoculations at booting and flowering produced the lowest yield parameters.

Yields ranged from 3.8 to 5.6 t/ha in IR42 and from 3.7 to 5.6 t/ha in IR72.

Table 2. Yield components and yield loss in 2 rice cultivars inoculated at different growth stages, 1988-89.^a

Treatment	Productive tillers (%)	Grain wt/plant (g)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1000-grain weight (g)	Filled grains (%)	Total biomass/plant (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
<i>IR42</i>								
Tillering	89.30 b	18.22 ab	49.00 a	17.98 ab	72.90 a	50.68 a	4.2 b	24.01 a
Panicle initiation	81.30 bc	17.10 b	46.00 a	17.60 bc	72.80 a	49.20 a	4.2 b	23.08 a
Booting	79.00 c	12.98 c	47.00 a	16.53 c	62.80 b	39.18 b	4.2 b	23.01 a
Flowering	87.50 b	16.15 b	46.00 a	18.13 a	64.80 b	42.50 b	3.8 b	32.15 a
Control	100.00 a	20.45 a	51.00 a	19.13 a	76.30 a	52.48 a	5.6 a	
<i>IR72</i>								
Tillering	91.30 b	21.97 b	41.00 a	23.75 a	71.2 b	46.70 ab	4.9 b	13.53 b
Panicle initiation	88.50 b	17.50 c	42.00 a	22.15 b	69.90 bc	42.00 bc	4.8 b	15.40 b
Booting	83.80 b	13.83 d	37.00 ab	21.73 bc	63.80 cd	42.40 bc	4.4 b	21.05 b
Flowering	89.30 b	12.98 d	28.00 b	20.68 c	62.00 d	37.95 c	3.7 c	34.83 a
Control	99.90 a	24.95 a	41.00 a	24.25 a	82.60 a	54.20 a	5.6 a	
CV (%)								
Cultivar	10.6	16.5	13.5	6.8	13.2	17.5	7.2	61.7
Treatment	6.2	10.6	14.2	3.8	7.0	9.4	9.6	30.0

^a Mean of 4 replications. In a column, mean followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Yields of control plots were significantly higher. In both cultivars, inoculation at flowering resulted in the lowest yields and highest yield loss.

Yield loss due to ShB may occur at any stage, but is higher when infection occurs at booting or flowering. ■

Comparison of rice sheath blight (ShB) assessment methods

N. R. Sharma and P. S. Teng, Plant Pathology Division, IRRI; and F. M. Olivares, Philippine Rice Research Institute, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines

We evaluated five methods for assessing ShB on three rice cultivars—highly susceptible IR72, susceptible IR64, and moderately resistant IR26957-86-2—in a pot experiment in the screenhouse during 1989 dry season. The methods were highest relative lesion height (HRLH %), disease severity (DS %), disease incidence (DI %), *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES), and real area infected (RAI %). RAI % was calculated by measuring the length and width of infected area.

Rice plants (5/pot) were inoculated with *Rhizoctonia solani* grown on rice grain-hull mixture (rice:hull = 1:3) at booting. Disease development was measured at 3-d intervals from inoculation, up to eight times. The area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was used to compare the three cultivars.

All assessment methods except DI gave the lowest AUDPC value in IR26957-86-2, confirming that IR26957-86-2 was more resistant to ShB infection than either IR64 or IR72 (see table).

All methods showed variable results among cultivars and also within each cultivar at different times of assessment (see table and figure).

Assessment by HRLH (%) is easy but tedious because each tiller in a hill must be evaluated.

Estimation of percent leaf and sheath area infected (DS) was faster than HRLH % and more efficient for evaluating a large amount of material within a short time. Assessment by DI showed that all tillers in a hill were infected within a few days of inoculation. But this method does not give total infection or an accurate assessment of DS—important data in epidemiological and yield loss studies.

ShB assessment by SES scale was easy and quick, but that method does not give a quantitative measure of real infection. For

AUDPC and standard error of 5 assessment methods applied to 3 rice cultivars, measured in a screenhouse experiment, 1988-89.^a

Method	AUDPC		
	IR64	IR72	IR26957-86-2
HRLH (%)	861.86 bx ± 29.00 (6.7)	828.11 bx ± 56.10 (13.5)	545.78 by p 31.50 (11.5)
DS (%)	437.81 cx ± 30.50 (14.0)	424.88 cx ± 19.30 (9.1)	317.63 cy p 51.20 (32.1)
DI (%)	2086.88 ax ± 1.88 (0.2)	2068.13 ax ± 12.25 (1.2)	2082.00 ax p 6.36 (0.6)
SES (0-9)	90.60 dx ± 5.20 (11.5)	85.91 ex ± 7.95 (17.6)	68.55 dx p 9.60 (28.1)
RAI (%)	386.01 cx ± 24.22 (12.7)	347.29 dxy ± 20.15 (11.6)	294.67 cy p 10.01 (6.7)

^a Mean of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter in a column (a, b, c) or in a row (x, y, z) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Figures within parentheses indicate CV (%).

Disease progress curves based on HRLH (%), DS (%), DI (%), SES, and real area infected for vertical development of ShB on 3 rice cultivars in the screenhouse. Each point is the mean of four replications. Vertical lines indicate standard errors.

quantitative data, actual measurement of injury is necessary.

Some difficulties were encountered in using RAI. Because infected leaves and sheaths have to be detached from the plant, the plant may be damaged before

maturity. The method is also tedious. At later growth stages, infected leaves and sheaths of lower plant parts cause difficulties in determining RAI. This method needs to be modified and tested for improved efficiency.

HRLH and DS are the most convenient and dependable assessment methods: they are easy to use and discriminate among cultivars. ■

Rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) on swamp rice in Guinea

S. N. Fomba, West Africa Rice Development Association, Mangrove Swamp Rice Research Program, P.M.B. 678, Freetown, Sierra Leone

Symptoms of presumed RYMV were observed on cultivated rice in mangrove and inland swamps of Coyah and Koba Districts, lower Guinea, 1982-1986. The chrysomelid beetle vectors of RYMV, *Chaetocnema* sp., were also observed at the same sites.

In 1986, some naturally infected rice plants were collected from a mangrove swamp at Yelimangeya, Coya District, and maintained in buckets on a 180-d duration, virus-susceptible rice cultivar CP4 at Rokupr, Sierra Leone. Similar naturally virus-infected rice plants were collected at Rokupr and Makoth in Kambia District and at Kabala in Koinadugu District in the Northern Province of Sierra Leone in 1988 and 1989 cropping seasons. These isolates

were maintained on CP4 by the same method.

In 1989, agar-gel double diffusion tests were done with crude extracts from virus-infected rice plants that had typical pale yellow mottling symptoms. Viruliferous saps were extracted in 0.01 M phosphate buffer solution, pH 7. (Antiserum was obtained from IITA.)

Reactions of virus antigens and antiserum were strongly positive. No spur formation was observed between the virus isolates of Guinea and Sierra Leone and the antiserum from Nigeria. This indicates serological similarity between RYMV isolates and probably their common identity. ■

Hosts of rice tungro-associated viruses (RTVs) in Thailand

A. Parejarearn, D. Chettanachit, M. Putta, W. Rattanakarn, J. Arayapan, and S. Disthaporn, Rice Pathology Group, Plant Pathology and Microbiology Division, Agriculture Department, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

We used enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and latex agglutination test to detect rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in 10 weed species, 12

species of wild rice, 27 lines of wild rice, wheat, barley, and maize.

The plants were inoculated separately with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* that had fed on RTVs-infected rice plants for 4 d. Each species had uninoculated plants as control. The vectors were confined on test plants at 5 insects/seedling for 24 h of inoculation. Inoculated seedlings were kept in the greenhouse.

The second youngest leaf of each plant was collected 30 days after inoculation and homogenized with phosphate buffer saline. Extracts of